

IMPACT OF STUDENT INTEREST AND MULTIMEDIA INSTRUCTION ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the impact of student interest and multimedia instruction on academic performance in mathematics in a college in Gingoog City, Philippines. Using a descriptive correlational research design, the study analyzed the effects of student interest and multimedia instruction on academic performance. A proportionate stratified random sampling method was used to select 120 participants from five different programs at the college, with 112 students responding. The research instruments, adapted from other studies, were modified and pilot tested for validity and reliability before distribution via Google Forms. Quantitative statistical methods, including mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's correlation, were employed to analyze the data. The findings indicate that while students consistently show interest in the subject, this enthusiasm does not significantly correlate with their academic performance. Similarly, multimedia instruction is perceived as moderately effective in enhancing learning experiences, yet it also does not significantly correlate with academic performance. Nonetheless, the majority of students achieved very good academic results by the end of the semester. These results suggest that while student interest and multimedia tools are important in education, their direct influence on academic performance may be affected by additional, unexplored factors.

Keywords: *student interest, multimedia instruction, academic performance*

INTRODUCTION

Poor Academic performance in mathematics remains a significant concern. In terms of country means, the Philippines placed second to last in mathematics in the local context, as revealed by the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) scores (Department of Education, 2019). Specifically, 18.5% of students attained the PISA 2018 minimum standard, which is level 2 or higher; 26.9% of students demonstrated level 1 proficiency; and 54.6% of Filipino students who took part received a score below the lowest level 1 proficiency (Department of Education, 2019). Furthermore, in the study of Capuno et al. (2019), it states that there is a need for development in the mathematical proficiency of Filipino students. As shown in the 2016–2017 Global Competitiveness Report, the Philippines ranked 79th out of the 138 countries in terms of the quality of science and math education.

According to a research study by Remo (2019), students' academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW) at Bukidnon State University in the Philippines was deemed fairly satisfactory, suggesting the need for improvement. Similarly, it was also found by Roman and Villanueva (2019) that students from the other selected state universities in the Philippines performed satisfactorily in the same subject; however, they had trouble with several areas.

Mathematics, being abstract in nature, often leads many students to lose interest, resulting in low achievement (Yeh et al., 2019). Beyond the inherent abstractness of mathematics, anxiety about learning the subject also plays a significant role in students' disinterest (Summer, 2020). Hence, interest is a crucial factor affecting students' achievement in mathematics (Yeh et al., 2019). Moreover, students who lack interest in mathematics are less likely to pay attention to the topic, and students who struggle to achieve good results in mathematics tests often exhibit weaknesses in fundamental mathematical skills (Minarni et al., 2016). Students who repeatedly score poorly in mathematics may eventually lose interest (Yeh et al., 2019). On the other hand, Yu and Singh's (2016) study's findings indicated that the relationship between interest and mathematics performance was insignificant. They further explained that interest might not be a direct predictor of mathematics performance.

The integration of multimedia technologies in classrooms has significantly revolutionized education. Multimedia instruction has great intentions in terms of enhancing learning across diverse student populations and educational levels. In addition, according to Tayirova (2023), the integration of multimedia tools in learning brings about positive effects on students, boosting their interest in learning, as well as students' development of self-confidence and motivation for self-improvement in learning. In the study of Wideasanti (2023), it was also stated that multimedia offers effective learning tools and fosters creativity and innovation in the learning environment, leading to improved learning quality and a more positive educational experience for students. An important advantage of using multimedia in mathematics is the increased interaction between students and concepts, along with the practical application of the skills they learn (Orlando & Attard, 2016).

In a learning setting with increased technology, Wong and Wong (2019), discovered that although children usually demonstrated interest in mathematics, there was no significant correlation between interest in mathematics and overall performance on a mathematics test administered to 40 students and the Mathematics Interest Inventory.

In the modern world, this study aims to uncover the profound impact of student interest and multimedia instruction on academic performance in mathematics. Through exploring these relationships, the study endeavors to address pertinent questions, such as the level of student interest, the role of multimedia tools in facilitating understanding, and their correlation with academic performance among participants who completed the Mathematics in the Modern World subject.

Research Questions

This study endeavors to ascertain the impact of student interest and multimedia instruction on academic performance in mathematics in the modern world school year 2023-2024.

More specifically, this research aims to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of student's interest in second semester Mathematics in the Modern World classes?
2. How do students perceive the effectiveness of multimedia instruction in enhancing their understanding of mathematical concepts in Mathematics in the Modern World classes?
3. What is the average academic performance of students in second semester Mathematics in the Modern World classes?
4. Is there a significant relationship between student interest and academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World?
5. Is there a significant relationship between multimedia instruction and academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World?

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the study is presented in this section. It discusses the research design, study location, subjects and participants, data collection procedure, including research instrument and validity and reliability testing, data processing system, analytical schemes, and statistical tools.

Locale and Sampling

The study was conducted in one of the Higher Education Institution in Gingoog City. It employed a descriptive correlational research design and utilized a proportionate stratified random sampling method to ensure a representative sample from the population. The sample is comprised of 120 first-year and second-year students from the

different academic programs offered mathematics in the modern world in a college in Gingoog City, Philippines. These programs include Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA), Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English (BSEd-English), Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), and Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA). A total of 112 participants participated in the study out of the target sample size of 120 participants.

Specific Data Gathering Procedure

After confirming the questionnaire's validity and reliability, the researcher obtained formal approval from the Research Adviser and the Dean of the target college by submitting a request letter. Upon receiving the necessary permissions, the researcher established a schedule for data collection. The research questionnaires were then distributed online via Google Forms, with the official consent of the Dean. Throughout the study, the researcher provided a detailed explanation of the research objectives and personally administered the questionnaires to respondents.

The respondents were assured that their data would be kept strictly confidential, as outlined in the questionnaire. Finally, the collected data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS.

Research Instrument

This study utilized adapted and revised questionnaires from the Mathematics Interest Inventory (MII) developed by Flaga (2021) and the Multimedia Instruction Inventory by Wao (2016) consisting of 20 items respectively. These instruments were subjected to a validation process and underwent pilot testing with a sample of 20 third-year BSEd-English and BEED students at a private college in Gingoog City who had taken the Mathematics in the Modern World subject. To establish internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was computed, resulting in values of 0.904 and 0.957, indicating excellent reliability.

Data Analysis

To gain a thorough grasp of the data, the following statistical tools were employed:

For problems number 1, 2, and 3, descriptive statistics such as mean and the standard deviation were used in order to determine the respondent's level of interest, perceive effectiveness of multimedia instruction, and academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World.

For problems 4 and 5, the Pearson correlation coefficient was utilized to determine whether there was a significant relationship between the respondents' level of interest in Mathematics in the Modern World and academic performance, and between respondents' perceived effectiveness of multimedia instruction in Mathematics in the Modern World and academic performance. This analysis helped in identifying the strength and direction of these relationships.

Scope and Limitations

The study utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to measure the level of interest, perceived effectiveness of multimedia instruction, and academic performance in mathematics in the modern world of college students during the second semester of the school year 2023–2024 in a college in Gingoog City, Philippines. One hundred twenty first-year and second-year students are sampled from the population; hence, there are only one hundred twelve respondents who responded to the research survey since researchers do not have control over respondents who choose not to participate during data collection. An adapted research instrument was employed to gather all the necessary data, which the study respondents provided by completing a survey questionnaire. SPSS was used to analyze the data, which included frequency count, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation coefficient.

RESULTS

Table 1.

Mean and Standard Deviation, Distribution of student's interest in Mathematics in the Modern World classes.

	Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1	I like to answer questions in Mathematics in the Modern World.	3.06	.701	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
2	I am interested in Mathematics in the Modern World.	3.05	.708	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
3	Knowing a lot about Mathematics in the Modern World is helpful.	3.36	.656	Strongly Agree	Exhibited and manifested at all times.
4	I feel happy when it comes to working on Math problems.	2.88	.807	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
5	I am excited when a new Math topic is introduced.	2.92	.807	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
6	I work hard in my Mathematics in the Modern World Class.	3.19	.665	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
7	I want to learn more about Mathematics.	3.20	.695	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
8	I believe I can get better and better at Math each day.	3.15	.674	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time

9	I complete all my Math assignments outside of class.	3.21	.646	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
10	I like doing mathematics activities.	2.90	.771	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
11	I think I have done well in mathematics during the second semester.	3.05	.708	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
12	Math can be a lot of fun.	3.12	.720	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
13	Discussing different solutions is a good way of learning math.	3.29	.663	Strongly Agree	Exhibited and manifested at all times.
14	I ask questions when I am unsure of a problem.	3.25	.717	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
15	I'm certain I can figure out how to solve difficult math problems.	2.88	.803	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
16	Time spent learning why a solution works is time well spent.	3.13	.651	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
17	I give math assignments my best effort.	3.26	.720	Strongly Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
18	Even if the concepts in math class are hard, I can learn them.	3.13	.673	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
19	It's important for me to do really well in math.	3.21	.621	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
20	I work on Mathematics in my spare time.	2.87	.753	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time
	Overall Mean	3.23	.644	Agree	Manifested and exhibited most of the time

Table 2.

Mean and Standard Deviation, Distribution of how students perceive the effectiveness of multimedia instruction in Mathematics in the Modern World classes.

	Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1	I can easily understand the topic of Mathematics in the Modern World with the integration of multimedia technology.	3.05	.642	Agree	Moderately effective
2	Multimedia instruction caught my interest in the class.	3.04	.629	Agree	Moderately effective
3	I don't need to copy some notes when multimedia is used.	2.79	.843	Agree	Moderately effective
4	Through multimedia instruction, it is easy for me to remember the details.	3.01	.678	Agree	Moderately effective
5	I feel sleepy and bored when it uses unattractive multimedia technology lessons.	2.81	.742	Agree	Moderately effective
6	I can easily acquire more information accurately and briefly when it uses multimedia teaching.	3.08	.617	Agree	Moderately effective
7	I am attentive when presentation is well-done.	3.29	.653	Strongly Agree	Highly effective
8	With multimedia instruction, I retain information for a longer period of time.	3.02	.629	Agree	Moderately effective
9	Multimedia stimulates my attention in class.	3.09	.578	Agree	Moderately effective
10	I don't want to pay attention when multimedia technology is not understandable.	2.88	.803	Agree	Moderately effective
11	I compare and contrast things easily with the aid of multimedia technology.	3.04	.576	Agree	Moderately effective
12	I acquire broader knowledge about the topic when multimedia technology is properly used.	3.12	.581	Agree	Moderately effective
13	I will not be satisfied if the multimedia presentation lacks follow up discussion.	3.01	.651	Agree	Moderately effective

14	Multimedia technology helps develop my mathematical skills.	3.15	.603	Agree	Moderately effective
15	I understand the lesson thoroughly and systematically through integration of multimedia technology.	3.15	.557	Agree	Moderately effective
16	I participate with the use of multimedia technology during discussion especially if it employs animation, sound, motion, or graphs.	3.04	.606	Agree	Moderately effective
17	Using multimedia technology inspires me to participate in class.	3.04	.629	Agree	Moderately effective
18	Instructional Materials like laptop and television excites me.	3.07	.667	Agree	Moderately effective
19	I feel enlighten when multiple multimedia instructional tools are used.	3.12	.611	Agree	Moderately effective
20	It encourages me to share my own thoughts and additional information if there is multimedia technology during the discussion.	2.96	.643	Agree	Moderately effective
Overall Mean		3.21	.505	Agree	Moderately effective

Table 3.

Frequency, Percentage, Mean Distribution, and Standard Deviation of the average academic performance of students in mathematics in the modern world classes

Grade Point Equivalence	Equivalence	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage %
1.00-1.50	90% - 100%	Excellent	35	31.3
1.60-2.00	85% - 89%	Very Good	37	33.0
2.10-2.50	80% - 84%	Good	39	34.8
2.60-3.00	75% - 79%	Passed	1	.9
3.10-5.00	Below 75%	Failed	0	0
Total			112	100

Mean: 1.82

Interpretation: Very Good

Standard Deviation: .403

Table 4.

Pearson Correlation Analysis of the significant relationship between student interest and academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World.

Variable	Academic Performance	
Student Interest	Pearson Correlation (r)	-.066
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.487
	Interpretation	Not significant

Table 5.

Pearson Correlation Analysis of the significant relationship between multimedia instruction and academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World.

Variable	Academic Performance	
Multimedia Instruction	Pearson Correlation (r)	-.049
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.607
	Interpretation	Not significant

DISCUSSION

1. What is the level of student's interest in second semester Mathematics in the Modern World classes?

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation distribution of students' interest levels in Mathematics in the Modern World. The overall mean of 3.2 indicates that students generally "agree" with statements regarding their interest, suggesting their interest is exhibited most of the time. Researchers observed that most students are engaged with the subject matter, demonstrating a generally positive interest. However, this level of interest does not represent the highest possible engagement, indicating room for improvement through innovative teaching methods or more engaging materials. Maass et al. (2019) note that boosting interest and performance in mathematics through such innovations is challenging and requires significant teacher commitment and motivation. Similarly, Mazana et al. (2019) found that an enjoyable learning environment significantly impacts students' interest in mathematics and enhances their performance.

The indicator with the highest mean ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 0.656$) was "Knowing a lot about Mathematics in the Modern World is helpful," showing that respondents strongly agree with its importance. Sharma's (2021) study supports this, as 82% of participants felt that knowledge of mathematics is beneficial in daily life. Mathematics fosters logical, critical, and creative thinking, and enhances problem-solving abilities, abstract and spatial

reasoning, and communication skills. It is essential in professional settings and provides financial opportunities, making it invaluable in our evolving world. Moreover, the statement "Discussing various solutions is a good way of learning math" had the second-highest mean ($M = 3.29$, $SD = 0.663$), indicating strong belief in the effectiveness of discussing multiple solutions. Stupel and Ben-Chaim's (2017) study supports this, showing that diverse approaches improve mathematical creativity and comprehension. Teachers should encourage and request multiple solutions in tests and classroom activities.

The indicator with the lowest mean ($M = 2.87$, $SD = 0.753$) was "I work on mathematics in my spare time," suggesting that respondents rarely engage with mathematics during leisure time. This trend may be due to factors such as lack of interest, math anxiety, or competing priorities. Ramirez et al. (2016) found that math anxiety significantly reduces students' willingness to engage with math outside of the classroom. Zimmerman et al. (2017) highlight the importance of self-regulation and motivation in influencing students' engagement with academic subjects beyond formal education. In addition, the indicators such as "I like to answer questions in Mathematics in the Modern World," "I am interested in Mathematics in the Modern World," "I feel happy when it comes to working on Math problems," and others, reflect students' emotions, self-efficacy, and mindset towards mathematics. A student's interest in their studies is influenced by various factors, including feelings, self-efficacy, and sense of community (Kahu et al., 2017). These indicators suggest that respondents are generally interested in the subject.

2. How do students perceive the effectiveness of multimedia instruction in enhancing their understanding of mathematical concepts in Mathematics in the Modern World classes?

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation distribution of students' perceptions of the effectiveness of multimedia instruction in enhancing their understanding of mathematical concepts in Mathematics in the Modern World classes. With an overall mean of 3.2054, or approximately 3.2, the respondents "agree" that multimedia instruction is moderately effective. The researchers observed that most students agree that multimedia instruction enhances their understanding of mathematical concepts. A strong foundation in basic mathematical concepts is a fundamental skill every student should possess. The correct and effective implementation of multimedia instruction can help students achieve a thorough understanding of concepts and excel in mathematics. This highlights the importance of continuous curriculum development and the integration of information and communications technology in education.

The specific indicator with the highest mean ($M = 3.29$, $SD = 0.653$) was "I am attentive when the presentation is well-done." This suggests that respondents strongly agree that a well-done presentation enhances their attentiveness. Yaftian and Barghamadi (2022) found that new teaching media improve student learning through intuitive observation and understanding, leading to greater involvement and responsiveness in the classroom, increased enthusiasm, and reduced anxiety about mathematical concepts. Multimedia instruction makes students more interested in learning mathematics. Moreover, the indicators "Multimedia technology helps develop my

mathematical skills" ($M = 3.15$, $SD = 0.603$) and "I understand the lesson thoroughly and systematically through the integration of multimedia technology" ($M = 3.15$, $SD = 0.557$) had the second highest means. Participants agree that multimedia instruction enhances their mathematical skills and deepens their understanding comprehensively and systematically. Biffi et al. (2019) found that interactive multimedia modules improved material transfer by 20%, knowledge retention by 8%, and satisfaction rates with course preparation significantly.

The indicator with the lowest mean ($M = 2.79$, $SD = 0.843$) was "I don't need to copy some notes when multimedia is used." This suggests that participants agree that note-taking is less necessary when multimedia is integrated into instruction. Akinoso (2020) found that using multimedia improves mathematics learning more than traditional instruction, allowing students to focus on learning rather than copying notes. In addition, the indicator "I feel sleepy and bored when it uses unattractive multimedia technology lessons" ($M = 2.81$, $SD = 0.742$) had the second lowest mean, indicating that unappealing multimedia technology makes participants feel disengaged. Heidig et al. (2016) found that the design of multimedia learning material affects learners' emotional states, impacting their intrinsic motivation to stay attentive and awake during lessons.

Overall, the results indicate that interactive multimedia instruction is effective in improving respondents' understanding of mathematical concepts. It provides flexibility and convenience for students, helping them engage in classroom activities and participate actively in their learning.

3. What is the average academic performance of students in second semester Mathematics in the Modern World classes?

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of participants' average academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World. The overall mean for the second semester of the 2023-2024 school year is 1.8, with a standard deviation of 0.403, indicating that the participants' academic performance in this subject is "very good." Most students had a grade point equivalence range of 2.10 to 2.50, corresponding to 80% to 84%, and a percentage of 34.8%, classifying them as "good" in Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW). Bangalan and Hipona (2022) found that students in this course exhibited a favorable disposition, recognizing its importance in both personal and societal contexts, and thrived in an environment that promoted curiosity, creative thinking, cooperation, love, and respect.

The school's grading system was used to measure students' academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World. Out of the 112 participants, none failed the subject, and only one student had a grade range of 2.60–3.00, equivalent to 75%–79%, representing 0.9% of the sample. Students who excelled with a grade point equivalence of 1.00–1.50, equivalent to 90%–100%, had a frequency of 35, representing 31.3%. Although the majority of respondents performed well, the data suggest there is room for improvement in their academic performance.

4. Is there a significant relationship between student interest and academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World?

Table 4 displays the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and the associated p-value (sig.) at the 0.05 significance level. The computed r value of -0.066 indicates a weak negative correlation between student interest and academic performance. The p-value of 0.487 exceeds the conventional significance level of 0.05, suggesting that this correlation is not statistically significant. Consequently, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no significant correlation between student interest and academic performance. This finding aligns with the studies of Wong and Wong (2019) and Yu and Singh (2016), both of which reported no substantial correlation between students' interest in mathematics and their academic performance.

Wong and Wong (2019) argue that students who excel in mathematics often do so due to external influences rather than intrinsic interest. These students may approach their studies with disciplined study habits and a strong grasp of foundational concepts. Their academic success in mathematics may not necessarily depend on their level of interest in the subject; rather, it could be attributed to effective study strategies and a methodical approach to learning.

5. Is there a significant relationship between multimedia instruction and academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World?

Table 5 displays the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and its associated p-value at the 0.05 significance level. The calculated r value of -0.049 suggests a very weak negative correlation between academic performance and multimedia instruction. The p-value of 0.607, which is higher than the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicates that this correlation is not statistically significant. Consequently, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, implying that there is no significant evidence to suggest that multimedia instruction has a meaningful impact on academic performance.

This finding is consistent with Akinoso's (2018) experimental study, which found that while multimedia use can somewhat improve students' learning and achievement in mathematics, these improvements were not statistically significant. This result contrasts with Khan et al.'s (2020) study, which reported that multimedia instruction significantly enhances academic performance among secondary and higher secondary school students.

Conclusions

The study aimed to determine the impact of student interest and multimedia instruction on academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World. Based on this premise, the following conclusions were drawn:

This study, conducted with 112 college students, investigated the impact of student interest and multimedia instruction on their academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World for the 2023-2024 school year. The findings reveal that while students

consistently express interest in the subject, this enthusiasm does not significantly correlate with their academic performance. Similarly, although multimedia instruction is perceived as moderately effective in enhancing learning experiences, it also shows no significant correlation with academic outcomes. Despite these observations, the majority of students achieved very good academic results by the end of the semester. This suggests that while student interest and multimedia tools play roles in education, their impact on actual academic performance may be influenced by additional factors not explored in this study. Other variables, such as individual learning styles, teaching strategies, and external factors, may also significantly affect students' academic achievements.

The results indicate a baseline level of proficiency among students, despite varying levels of perceived interest and instructional effectiveness. This highlights the need for further investigation into how different instructional strategies and personalized approaches can better align with students' diverse learning needs and preferences. The use of a descriptive correlational research design, supported by careful data collection and analysis methods, strengthens the reliability and validity of the study's conclusions. However, the study acknowledges limitations such as its specific context and the potential challenges of generalizing findings across different educational settings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusions of the study, the researchers arrived at the following recommendations to the following entities:

1. to the math teachers that they may:

- 1.1 integrate different types of instructional methods with integration of digital application in their math classes;
- 1.2 use new and accessible digital materials in their math classes that may give dedication to students to strive more;
- 1.3 utilize multimedia learning materials that are comprehensible and student-friendly

2. to the students that they may:

- 2.1 read materials and engage themselves more to mathematics;
- 2.2 be motivated enough to do the tasks given and continue doing better; and
- 2.3 give some time to yourself and reflect on the things you want to achieve in life in order to be determined in doing any activities

3. to the school administration that they may:

- 3.1 provide more digital and traditional materials to the teacher and students and
- 3.2 conduct mathematics related activities to foster mathematics engagement and positive mindset of students.

4. to the future researchers that they may:

4.1 carry out improvements in line with the current study;

4.2 explore other factors in enhancing educational practices and outcomes in mathematics education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards to ensure the safety and well-being of all respondents. The research minimized the risk of harm by guaranteeing the confidentiality and anonymity of respondents' responses throughout and beyond the research process. Free, prior informed consent was obtained from all participants at the outset, with assurances provided regarding their right to withdraw from the study at any point. Adherence to protocols ensured voluntary respondents, maintaining the anonymity and confidentiality of responses, thereby protecting participants from any potential harm.

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